

Extensions of Newton-Type Inequalities via Multiplicative Conformable Fractional Integrals

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DOI : [10.5281/zenodo.18012198](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18012198)

Abstract

In this study, a novel form of Newton-type inequality for multiplicative convex functions is derived using multiplicative conformable fractional integrals, which has not been previously addressed in the literature. To prove the main results of the study, a well-structured integral identity is first established. This identity is then combined with multiplicative conformable fractional integrals to construct a new inequality structure. In addition, a special Newton-type inequality is presented for functions whose multiplicative derivatives are bounded. To support the validity of the obtained inequality and the derived identity, various specific cases are provided, thereby demonstrating the generality and flexibility of the results. In this respect, the study offers a new perspective to the field of multiplicative analysis and lays a foundation for future applications to different types of fractional integral operators or function classes.

Keywords: Multiplicative calculus, Newton inequality, fractional integrals, bounded function.

1 Introduction

Fractional calculus has been widely employed to describe nonlocal and memory-driven phenomena, leading to the development of various fractional integral operators with strong modeling capabilities [12, 1].

As an alternative to classical calculus, multiplicative calculus has emerged as an alternative analytical framework based on multiplication rather than addition, making it particularly effective for processes governed by exponential growth, decay, or proportional changes[15]. The foundations of multiplicative derivatives and integrals were formalized in[6], enabling the adaptation of classical inequalities to the multiplicative setting. Within this framework, several fundamental inequalities (such as Hermite–Hadamard and Ostrowski inequalities) have been extended to their multiplicative counterparts [2, 8, 4]. Chasreechai et al. obtained Newton-type inequalities for multiplicative integrals[11]. Subsequently, Ali presented Newton-type inequalities for the multiplicative Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals[2]. More recently, the multiplicative conformable fractional integral (MCFI) was introduced as a hybrid operator combining the advantages of both conformable and multiplicative calculus structures[9]. For more information, please refer to[11, 7, 10, 5].

This article consists of five sections, including the introduction. In Section 2, multiplicative derivatives and multiplicative integrals are reviewed, and the properties related to these concepts are presented. Then, the definitions of Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals, conformable fractional integrals, multiplicative Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals, and multiplicative conformable fractional integrals are introduced. In Section 3, an identity necessary for presenting the main findings is obtained. In Section 4, it is aimed to develop Newton-type inequalities for multiplicative differentiability and multiplicative convex functions with the help of MCFI. Finally, in Section 5, the results of our study are evaluated, and potential directions for future research are highlighted.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Multiplicative Calculus

Proposition 2.1. [6] If f is positive and Riemann integrable on $[a, b]$, then f is multiplicative integrable on $[a, b]$ and

$$\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} = \exp \left\{ \int_a^b \ln(f(x)) dx \right\}.$$

Proposition 2.2. [6] Under the condition that the functions f and g , being positive, are multiplicative integrable on the interval $[a, b]$, it is evident that the properties given below are applicable.

1. $\int_a^b ((f(x))^p)^{dx} = \left(\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} \right)^p, p \in \mathbb{R},$
2. $\int_a^b (f(x)g(x))^{dx} = \int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} \cdot \int_a^b (g(x))^{dx},$
3. $\int_a^b \left(\frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \right)^{dx} = \frac{\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx}}{\int_a^b (g(x))^{dx}},$
4. $\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} = \int_a^c (f(x))^{dx} \cdot \int_c^b (f(x))^{dx}, a \leq c \leq b,$
5. $\int_a^a (f(x))^{dx} = 1$ and $\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} = \left(\int_b^a (f(x))^{dx} \right)^{-1}.$

Definition 2.1. [6] Consider the function $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ and assume that its $*$ derivative exists. The notation f^* symbolizes multiplicative derivative of f (shortly $*$ derivative of the function f), which is expressed as

$$f^*(x) = \frac{d^* f(x)}{dx} = \exp \left\{ (\ln f(x))' \right\}.$$

Proposition 2.3. [6] Presuming that the functions $f, g : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ are $*$ differentiable, and the function $h : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is differentiable on I° . If the constant $c > 0$, then the functions $cf, f + g, fg, \frac{f}{g}, f^h$ and $f \circ h$ are all $*$ differentiable on I° as well, and the listed below properties holds:

1. $(cf)^*(x) = f^*(x),$
2. $(f + g)^*(x) = [f^*(x)]^{\frac{f(x)}{f(x)+g(x)}} [g^*(x)]^{\frac{g(x)}{f(x)+g(x)}},$
3. $(fg)^*(x) = f^*(x)g^*(x),$
4. $\left(\frac{f}{g} \right)^*(x) = \frac{f^*(x)}{g^*(x)},$
5. $(f^h)^*(x) = f^*(x)^{h(x)} f(x)^{h'(x)},$
6. $(f \circ h)^*(x) = f^*(h(x))^{h'(x)}.$

Definition 2.2 (Multiplicative absolute value). [14] Let $x \in \mathbb{R}_*$. The multiplicative absolute value is defined as follows

$$|x|_* = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x \geq 1, \\ \frac{1}{x}, & \text{if } 0 < x < 1. \end{cases}$$

Remark 2.1. The classical absolute value and the multiplicative one are linked by the following relation

$$|\exp\{x\}|_* = \exp|x|$$

and

$$|\ln(x)| = \ln|x|_*.$$

The following theorems give the integral-by-part formulas for multiplicative integrals, which will be used in the main results.

Theorem 2.1. [6] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be multiplicative differentiable and $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be differentiable so the f^g is multiplicative integrable. Then

$$\int_a^b \left((f^*(x))^{g(x)} \right)^{dx} = \frac{(f(b))^{g(b)}}{(f(a))^{g(a)}} \cdot \frac{1}{\int_a^b \left((f(x))^{g'(x)} \right)^{dx}}.$$

Theorem 2.2. [4] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be multiplicative differentiable, let $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $h : I \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [a, b]$ be two differentiable functions. Then we have

$$\int_a^b \left((f^*(h(x)))^{g(x)h'(x)} \right)^{dx} = \frac{f(h(b))^{g(b)}}{f(h(a))^{g(a)}} \cdot \frac{1}{\int_a^b \left((f(h(x)))^{g'(x)} \right)^{dx}}.$$

2.2 Some Definitions and Several Newton Inequalities

Definition 2.3. [22] A non-empty set K is said to be convex, if for every $a, b \in K$ we have

$$a + t(b - a) \in K, \forall t \in [0, 1].$$

Definition 2.4. [22] A function f is said to be convex function set K , if

$$f(tx + (1 - t)y) \leq tf(x) + (1 - t)f(y)$$

for all $a, b \in K$ and all $t \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.5. [19] A function f is said to be *log* or multiplicatively convex function on set K , if

$$f(ta + (1 - t)b) \leq [f(x)]^t [f(y)]^{(1-t)}$$

for all $a, b \in K$ and all $t \in [0, 1]$.

Remark 2.2. If a positive function f is a multiplicatively convex, then the function $\ln f$ is a convex function.

Definition 2.6. The Euler Gamma function, Beta function and Incomplete Beta function are defined by

$$\Gamma(x) := \int_0^\infty \xi^{x-1} e^{-\xi} d\xi$$

$$B(x, y) := \int_0^1 \xi^{x-1} (1 - \xi)^{y-1} d\xi$$

and

$$\mathfrak{B}(x, y, r) := \int_0^r \xi^{x-1} (1 - \xi)^{y-1} d\xi$$

respectively for $0 < x, y < \infty$ and $r \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.7. [18] Let the function $f \in L_1([a, b])$. For the order $\beta > 0$, the Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integrals (RLFI) $J_{a+}^\beta f(x)$ and $J_{b-}^\beta f(x)$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x (x - t)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b (t - x)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad b > x$$

respectively. Here Γ represents the Euler Gamma function.

Definition 2.8. [8] The multiplicative left Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integral $({}_a I_*^\beta f)(x)$ of order $\beta > 0$ starting from β is defined by

$$({}_a I_*^\beta f)(x) = \exp \left\{ (J_{a+}^\beta (\ln \circ f))(x) \right\}$$

and the multiplicative right one $(*_b I^\beta f)(x)$ is defined by

$$(*_b I^\beta f)(x) = \exp \left\{ (J_{b-}^\beta (\ln \circ f))(x) \right\}.$$

Definition 2.9. [16] Let the function $f \in L_1([a, b])$. For the order $\beta > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$, the Conformable Fractional Integrals (CFI) ${}_+^{\beta}I_a^{\alpha}f(x)$ and ${}_-^{\beta}I_b^{\alpha}f(x)$, correspondingly, are defined by

$${}_+^{\beta}I_a^{\alpha}f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(x-a)^{\alpha} - (t-a)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} (t-a)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, x > a$$

and

$${}_-^{\beta}I_b^{\alpha}f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \left(\frac{(b-x)^{\alpha} - (b-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} (b-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, b > x$$

respectively. Here, Γ represents the Euler Gamma function.

Definition 2.10. [10] The multiplicative left Conformable Fractional Integral $({}_a^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_*^{\alpha}f)(x)$ of order $\beta > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ by

$$\begin{aligned} ({}_a^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_*^{\alpha}f)(x) &= \exp \left\{ {}_+^{\beta}I_a^{\alpha}((\ln \circ f)(x)) \right\} \\ &= \exp \left\{ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(x-a)^{\alpha} - (t-a)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{(\ln \circ f)(t)}{(t-a)^{1-\alpha}} dt, x > a \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

and the multiplicative right Conformable Fractional Integral $({}_*^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha}f)(x)$ is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} ({}_*^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha}f)(x) &= \exp \left\{ {}_-^{\beta}I_b^{\alpha}((\ln \circ f)(x)) \right\} \\ &= \exp \left\{ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \left(\frac{(b-x)^{\alpha} - (b-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{(\ln \circ f)(t)}{(b-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, b > x \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Here, Γ is the Euler Gamma function.

3 An Essential Identity MCFI

Lemma 3.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be multiplicative differentiable function over (a, b) . If f^* is multiplicative integrable on $[a, b]$, then the following equality holds:

$$\frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta} \mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta} \mathcal{I}_a^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha\beta 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}} } = [T_1 \times T_2 \times T_3 \times T_4]^{\frac{\alpha\beta(b-a)}{4}}. \quad (1)$$

Here,

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta}} \right) dt, \\ T_2 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{-\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta}} \right) dt, \\ T_3 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{\left(\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta} - \frac{3}{4\alpha^{\beta}} \right)} \right) dt, \\ T_4 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{3}{4\alpha^{\beta}} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta} \right)} \right) dt, \end{aligned}$$

and Γ is Euler Gamma function.

Proof. By using Theorem 2.2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 & = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta}} \right) dt \\ & = \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta} \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)} \right) dt \right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2b+a}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)^0} \cdot \frac{1}{\left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) \right]^{\beta(1-t)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1}} \right) dt \right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}}} \\
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2b+a}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{\exp \left\{ \frac{2}{b-a} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \beta(1-t)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) dt \right\}} \\
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2b+a}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{\exp \left\{ \frac{2}{b-a} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \beta(b-u)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^\alpha(b-u)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(u) \frac{2}{b-a} du \right\}} \\
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2b+a}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{\exp \left\{ \frac{2^\alpha \beta + 1 \Gamma(\beta + 1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha \beta + 1} \Gamma(\beta)} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} (b-u)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{(b-a)^\alpha - (b-u)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(u) du \right\}},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_2 &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{-\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta} \right) dt \tag{3} \\
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{\exp \left\{ \frac{2^\alpha \beta + 1 \Gamma(\beta + 1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha \beta + 1} \Gamma(\beta)} \int_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (k-a)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^\alpha - (k-a)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(k) dk \right\}},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_3 &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right] \left(\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} \right) \right) dt \tag{4} \\
 &= \left[\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right] \left(\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} \right) \left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right) \right) dt \right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{[f(b)]^{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha\beta} - \frac{3}{4\alpha\beta}\right)\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)}}{\left[f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha\beta}\right]} \cdot \frac{1}{\left[\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(f\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right)\right)^{\beta(1-t)\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} dt\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}}} \\
&= \frac{[f(b)]^{\frac{1}{2(b-a)\alpha\beta}}}{\left[f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha\beta}\right]} \cdot \exp\left\{\frac{2}{b-a} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \beta(1-t)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) dt\right\} \\
&= \frac{[f(b)]^{\frac{1}{2(b-a)\alpha\beta}} \cdot \left[f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\frac{3}{4\alpha\beta} - \left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta\right]}}{\exp\left\{\frac{2}{b-a} \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \beta(b-u)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^\alpha(b-u)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(u) \frac{2}{b-a} du\right\}} \\
&= \frac{[f(b)]^{\frac{1}{2(b-a)\alpha\beta}} \cdot \left[f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\frac{3}{4\alpha\beta} - \left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta\right]}}{\exp\left\{\frac{2\alpha\beta+1}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta+1}\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b (b-u)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^\alpha - (b-u)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(u) du\right\}}
\end{aligned}$$

and similarly

$$\begin{aligned}
T_4 &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{3}{4\alpha\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right)} \right)^{dt} \\
&= \frac{[f(a)]^{\frac{1}{2(b-a)\alpha\beta}} \cdot \left[f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) \right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\frac{3}{4\alpha\beta} - \left(\frac{3^\alpha-1}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta\right]}}{\exp\left\{\frac{2\alpha\beta+1}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta+1}\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} (k-a)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^\alpha - (k-a)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(k) dk\right\}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

By multiplying the results of (2),(3),(4) and (5) and raising both sides of the obtained identity to the power of $\frac{(b-a)\alpha\beta}{4}$, we obtain the equality (1). \square

Corollary 3.1. If we pick $\alpha = 1$ in (1), then we obtain the next identity holds for MRLFI:

$$\frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^*I_b^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}_aI_*^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{2\beta-1}{(b-a)^\beta} \Gamma(\beta+1)}} = [K_1 \times K_2 \times K_3 \times K_4]^{\frac{b-a}{4}}.$$

Here,

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_1 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{t^\beta} \right)^{dt}, \\
 K_2 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{(-t^\beta)} \right)^{dt}, \\
 K_3 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{(t^\beta - \frac{3}{4})} \right)^{dt}, \\
 K_4 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{(\frac{3}{4} - t^\beta)} \right)^{dt}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.2. Picking $\beta = 1$ in Corollary 3.1, then we obtain the next identity holds for multiplicative integrals:

$$\frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[\int_a^b (f(t)) dt \right]^{\frac{1}{(b-a)}}} = [C_1 \times C_2 \times C_3 \times C_4]^{\frac{b-a}{4}}.$$

Here,

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_1 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^t \right)^{dt}, \\
 C_2 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{(-t)} \right)^{dt}, \\
 C_3 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{(t - \frac{3}{4})} \right)^{dt}, \\
 C_4 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{(\frac{3}{4} - t)} \right)^{dt}.
 \end{aligned}$$

4 On Newton Type Inequalities Involving Bounded Functions

In this section, we present several Newton type inequalities for functions with bounded multiplicative derivatives.

Theorem 4.1. Postulate that the constraints of Lemma 3.1 are satisfied. If there are $m, M \in \mathbb{R}^+$ so that $m \leq f^*(x) \leq M$ for all $x \in [a, b]$, then we have the following Newton type inequalities for MCFI

$$\left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_a^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha^{\beta} 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}}} \right|_* \leq \left(\frac{M}{m}\right)^{\frac{(b-a)\alpha^{\beta}}{4} [\Psi_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Psi_2(\alpha, \beta)]},$$

Here,

$$\Psi_1(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \mathcal{B}\left(\beta + 1, \frac{1}{\alpha}, 1 - \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha}\right)$$

and

$$\Psi_2(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{1/3}^1 \left| \frac{3}{4\alpha^{\beta}} - \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta} \right| dt$$

Proof. By using Lemma 3.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_a^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha^{\beta} 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}}} \\ &= \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^{\beta}(b-a)}{4} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta} \left(\ln f^*\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right) dt \right\} \\ & \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^{\beta}(b-a)}{4} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(-\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta}\right) \left(\ln f^*\left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b\right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right) dt \right\} \\ & \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^{\beta}(b-a)}{4} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta} - \frac{3}{4\alpha^{\beta}}\right) \left(\ln f^*\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right) dt \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

$$\times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right) \left(\ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right) dt \right\}.$$

Applying the $*$ -absolute value for the two sides of (6), yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_a^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha^\beta 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}}} \right| \tag{7} \\ & \leq \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| dt \right\} \\ & \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| dt \right\} \\ & \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| dt \right\} \\ & \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| dt \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since the function f^* is bounded and the function \ln is increasing, then the function $\ln f^*$ is bounded by $\ln m$ and $\ln M$. Thus we conclude

$$\left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| \leq \frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \tag{8}$$

and

$$\left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| \leq \frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2}. \tag{9}$$

By make use of (8) and (9), inequality (7) becomes

$$\left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_a^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha^\beta 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}}} \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left(\frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \right) \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt \right\} \\
&\quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left(\frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \right) \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt \right\} \\
&\quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left(\frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \right) \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} \right| dt \right\} \\
&\quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left(\frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \right) \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt \right\} \\
&= \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} (\ln M - \ln m) [\Psi_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Psi_2(\alpha, \beta)] \right\} \\
&= \left(\frac{M}{m} \right)^{\frac{(b-a)\alpha^\beta}{4} [\Psi_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Psi_2(\alpha, \beta)]}.
\end{aligned}$$

This ends the proof. \square

Corollary 4.1. If we set $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4.1, we obtain the next Newton-type inequality with MRLFI:

$$\left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}_a I_b^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}_a I_*^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{2\beta-1\Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^\beta}}} \right|_* \leq \left(\frac{M}{m} \right)^{\frac{b-a}{4} [\Omega_1(\beta) + \Omega_2(\beta)]}.$$

Here, the functions are defined as

$$\Omega_1(\beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} t^\beta dt = \frac{1}{3^{\beta+1}(\beta+1)},$$

and

$$\Omega_2(\beta) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^\beta \left[\frac{3(\beta+1)-3}{2(\beta+1)} \right] - \frac{\beta}{\beta+1} + \frac{1}{3^{\beta+1}(\beta+1)}, & 0 < \beta < \frac{\ln(3/4)}{\ln(1/3)}, \\ \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{\beta+1} + \frac{1}{3^{\beta+1}(\beta+1)}, & \beta > \frac{\ln(3/4)}{\ln(1/3)}. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 4.2. Setting $\beta = 1$ Corollary 4.1 gives the upcoming Newton type inequality

with multiplicative integrals:

$$\left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left(\int_a^b (f(t)) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{b-a}}} \right|_* \leq \left(\frac{M}{m} \right)^{\frac{(b-a)}{72}}.$$

5 Conclusion

In this study, we obtain an inequality involving bounded multiplicative derivatives by employing multiplicative conformable fractional integrals. To this end, a fundamental integral identity is first introduced, which forms the basis of our main result. Using this identity together with the framework of multiplicative conformable fractional calculus, a new type of Newton-type inequality is derived. For the obtained identity and the corresponding inequality, particular cases are examined to demonstrate the applicability of the results. As a direction for future research, the proposed approach may be adapted to alternative fractional integral operators to derive different Newton-type inequalities.

6 Acknowledgments

The authors thank the editors and reviewers for their constructive feedback, which helped improve the manuscript.

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